

PROFITING WATER MISMANAGEMENT: ARGUMENTATION ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL WATER POLICY OF PAKISTAN

Usman Umer¹, Muhammad Waqas Butt², Dr Asma Majeed^{*3}

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Media Studies, Govt. Associate College Sharaqpur, Sheikhpura

²Department of Gender Studies, University of the Punjab, Lahore

³Lecturer, Department of Applied Psychology, Kinnaird College for Women, Lahore

³asma.majeed@kinnaird.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

This paper is a critical discourse analysis and a critique of National Water Policy of Pakistan. It is argued that much cried water scarcity and emerging water crisis in Pakistan is more an issue of mismanagement of water resources and water distribution. Under the sway of neoliberal capitalist practices and subservience to international aid and regulatory bodies, Pakistani state officials are hiding their negligence and incapacities under the cover of climate change, population growth and urbanization. In order to commoditize water, the policymakers are framing strategically fortunate geographic location of Pakistan as a curse. Current studies about water resource management in Pakistan are silent about this aspect. Conducting critical discourse analysis as dialectical reasoning for the National Water Policy, this study highlights contradictions in policy statements, develops possible critique of arguments and provides counterarguments as a way of action for change. Policymakers have produced a patchwork in the name of comprehensive policy framework. Critical analysis reveals that this water policy is irrelevant to ground realities of Pakistan. The actual objective of the policy is to bring every drop of water under market-determined price mechanism and to create a real water crisis so that underpriced water becomes a high-priced commodity.

INTRODUCTION

Safe and clean drinking water is essential for healthy life but this existential need is becoming a thing having an economic value. Limited financial resources, lack of policy and planning and mismanagement of water resources are intensifying

challenges related to water in developing countries (Raza et al., 2017). Only 2.5% of earth's total water sources consist of freshwater (Mumtaz et al., 2017) and 30% of this freshwater is groundwater (Raza et al., 2017). This amount of groundwater is threatened

by consumption of water in industrial, domestic and agricultural sectors and increased demand of water because of growing population (Muhammad et al., 2016). Water contamination and shortage and climate change are global challenges that need global cooperation (Ahmad et al., 2023). Water resources management is thus crucial for Pakistan since a major proportion of population is dependent on fresh water supply. Water policy and planning in Pakistan attributes water scarcity to urbanization, climate change and population growth (Ahmad et al., 2023). However, this scarcity is also influenced by lack of infrastructure and inefficient methods in irrigation (Tayyab, 2022). Pakistan has taken many initiatives with the support of international bodies but institutional incapacities, bad governance and political instability are restricting the successful implementation of such measures (Ahmad et al., 2023).

National Water Policy 2018 (NWP) of Pakistan (Ministry of Water Resources, 2018) is a policy document that typically reflects how deliberations and efforts are invested to address national problems in Pakistan. This document claims to be based on existing nine “useful Reports and Studies” and intends to provide an “integrated Water Resource Management Strategy” (p. 2). This 41-page document is considered a comprehensive and well-thought national plan to manage water resources, with a 4-page Water Charter as appendix. This Water Charter is also boasted of as “historic moment”. The document consists of 30 sections resembling the format of an Act or Ordinance.

Aligning with but significantly departing from Ahmad et al. (2023) this paper argues that Pakistan’s National Water Policy 2018 is an ineffective mixture of neoliberal capitalist policy principles that will intensify water crisis instead of mitigating it. This policy is assumed to be influenced by imperialist global organizations that consistently follow and implement neoliberal capitalist agenda. Drew & Crase (2023) have found that Asian Development Bank and World Bank were involved in the formulation of this policy. They also analyzed that “More Crop per Drop” strategy proposed by the policy for water conservation in irrigation is unsound and will potentially increase water use. Though the policy claims collaboration and participation of all

stakeholders but in fact farmers have no idea of drip irrigation and sprinkling methods of irrigation that the policy has proposed. They further doubted the coupling of water security with national security in the policy.

The securitization of water in NWP is favored and justified by Mirza & Mahmood (2023). They have argued that “non-traditional security issues” such as water scarcity may prove devastating for the society and state if they are not securitized. Second justification is that securitization of a non-traditional security issue creates public support. Third justification is that civil society groups are also involved in legitimizing the securitization of such issues. Main actors in securitization of water scarcity are politicians who do this for the sake of attracting voters. They describe that de-securitization phase comes when the policy objectives are met. Through these justifications Drew & Crase (2023) support not only securitization of water scarcity but also appreciate the World Bank’s “more crop per drop” strategy proposed in NWP. Although, the policy frames water crisis as a security issue of national imperative yet there is no mention of consultation and involvement of national security agencies (Sumra et al., 2020).

Büscher & Arsel (2012) have already criticized neoliberal strategies for environmental conservation. According to their view these neoliberal strategies are intended to make capitalism compatible with conservation and to turn this conservation into a source for economic growth (Büscher & Arsel, 2012). The United Nations and world leaders are emphasizing green technology and green economy. Their argument is that capitalist system is trying to “safeguard future economic growth” by incorporating pollution, loss of water resources, loss of biodiversity and climate change. The academic and policy debates are silent about role of capitalism in environmental degradation (Büscher & Arsel, 2012). Our view is that capitalist system and mode of production is not only resolved from the responsibility of damaging nature and environment but it is also presented as a hero and savior of environment and humanity. Generally, human rights framework is adopted by international organizations to promote capitalist agendas. Karunanathan (2018) reviews “Right to Water” literature and finds that

such campaigns delegitimize “the State as duty-bearer” meaning that the state is financially and technically incapable of fulfilling its responsibility of providing water to its citizens. Second discourse is to delegitimize citizens as water users assuming them “unworthy rights-holder” who are wasting water and are self-interested. Third discourse legitimizes market as efficient manager and distributor of water resources than the incompetent state. NWP declares water as fundamental human right but the planning and strategies adopted delegitimize the state, affirm its mismanagement, presume self-interested citizens indulged in wasteful practices and legitimize market as fair and neutral arbiter. The policy fails to distinguish short-term and long-term goals, ignores civic engagement and adopts an unrealistic and unscientific approach (Sumra et al., 2020).

This brief introduction and overview of NWP presents the scenario and context in which the policy document is analyzed. We find that existing studies on NWP have identified several flaws in the policy but none of these has analyzed neoliberal biases and potential risks of commodification of water. The central argument of this paper is that it will be better and fortunate for the people of Pakistan if this policy is not implemented. Therefore this paper does not engage merits of the policy or flaws in its implementation and lack of project financing.

OBJECTIVE AND METHOD

This paper analyses the discourses and arguments presented by the policymakers in NWP. The primary objective is to reveal contradictions in the policy statements, identify inconsistencies in premises and conclusions and implicit values. The aim is to deconstruct the policy discourses by identifying the underlying neoliberal ideology of market supremacy. This deconstruction is aimed to present an alternative view to Pakistani academia and to create awareness about the future situation of water availability if these policy proposals are realized. This qualitative study has applied Fairclough’s (2019) dialectical reasoning method (argumentation analysis, practical reasoning) of critical discourse analysis to analyze policy debates and documents. In this method, arguments in the text are identified and analyzed in the light of existing realities; claims are scrutinized and argumentative conclusions are

assessed in terms of their consequences; and counter-arguments are developed to change terms of debate aiming at possible change. This possible change or action may include resistance or introduction of alternative discourse to challenge the dominant discourse and ideology.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The Preamble of the NWP briefly highlights importance and value of water system and water resources, current and potential water related risks, existing studies and reports, the need for the national water policy, intensity of water crisis and major concerns of water sector in Pakistan. The Preamble starts with the premise that Pakistan’s irrigation system is “one of the largest contiguous irrigated systems in the World” that is continuously recharged by monsoon waters and snow-melts. This claim is well-supported and no doubt Pakistan’s irrigation network is remarkably extensive. This claim mentions impressive size of the system but blackouts its efficiency and sustainability. It does mention “siltation” of dams and storage concerns (p. 4) but neglects waterlogging, salinity and infrastructural deficiencies that constrain and question the practical value of this “extensive” system. Second premise is that “Pakistan is heading towards a situation of water shortage” with “rapidly growing population” (p. 1). The document states that per capita water availability is drastically reduced to 1000 cubic meters in 2016. This premise highlights “growing population” (2%) as the single responsible pressure and threat to water availability and discursively ignores management and efficiency of water resources by the state authorities. It may be partially true that population growth is a significant factor in water crisis but water mismanagement, lack of policy reforms and inefficient irrigation practices are more responsible and crucial. Solely shouldering the responsibility of water crisis to the “population growth” entails that de-growth of population, irrespective of management of water resources, is the natural solution to the water crisis. Circumstantial evidence from other countries belies this claim. There are many countries that have higher population growth rate than that of Pakistan (1.9%) but many of those are not haunted with such sort of population pressures. Singapore, for example, has

annual population growth of 3.3% however there is no water scarcity or water crisis due to efficient conservation and management of water. The document pairs population growth with rapid and unregulated urbanization as cause of water crisis. Again, this indicates inefficiency and mismanagement of the state authorities more tellingly than the havoc of increasing number of citizens. Urbanization trends and planning and its regulation is the responsibility of the state authorities who have not paid attention to this problem. This indicates lack of vision and policies from the government. Urbanization is a global phenomenon and there are many times more urbanized areas in the world than in Pakistan but those are considered ideal locations for Pakistanis due to progress and development there. On the one hand, population growth increase the number of citizens of a state and increases manpower and human capital but on the other hand the same human capital is abhorred. This contradiction seems to be unresolved in Pakistan.

The policy discourse then shifts from national to global factors. Third premise is that climate change, unpredicted rainfall patterns and glacier melting are contributing to water scarcity and floods. This premise is again contradictory and reflects mismanagement. Climate change is indeed a serious problem but actual concern is what is being done to reduce this environmental phenomenon. If glacier melting leads to floods then it means water is not scarce but there is wastage of water. Flood means abundance, not scarcity. If glacier melting is a problem then this should be diagnosed. If it is a modern problem caused by modern lifestyle and development then it means modern way living is problematic. Why is there no mention of changing this lifestyle? This premise reflects flawed rationality adopted in policy and planning. Adverse effects of rains and glacier melting can be successfully countered by enhancing water storage capacities, managing watershed and constructing reservoirs. Ironically, with this backdrop of inefficiency, mismanagement and myopic vision, the document hopes that implementation of “appropriate adaptation measures” will make it possible to “ensure water, food and energy security for the country” along with minimizing “the impact of natural disasters” (p. 1). This statement is simply over-

optimism an exaggeration, if not a bluff. The mentioned anonymous “adaptation measures” for quadric problems in fact demand management, governance, technological innovation and substantial infrastructure, precisely those factors that caused the problem in the first place. Note here the absence of population growth and urbanization, both of them the document identifies as the main culprits for water crisis, from these measures.

Mismanagement and contradictory explanations

In the next paragraphs the document states the objective of National Water Policy that is to develop a national framework and guidelines. Two other important claims or provincial autonomy and lack of coordination regarding water management. Lack of coordinated development is explained as caused by the issue that is “creeping slowly” and moderated by ground water abstraction through tube wells. This sort excusing explanation reveals contradictory framing of the issue. It entails that the issue that creeps slowly does not necessitate coordinated development and planning. It is only the gravity and intensity of the issue when measures are taken to tackle the issue. It means no precautions are needed. Moreover, this excuse reflects confidence that minor level issue needs no planning but the intensity and expansion of the issue at broader level is surely manageable. In other words, the suitable time to manage an issue is when it becomes immensely difficult to manage. Moreover, there is no guarantee that now the required political will and institutional capacity exists for coordination. The same logic is present in the claim of ground water abstraction through tube wells. The document accepts that “1 million” tube wells are extracting ground water that 20% more than the canal water. Note here that this fact is presented as an ease from the responsibility and as a good measure. This statement is explicit indicator of bad governance and historical mismanagement but it is framed positively. It means the public and the farmers are managing their water problems on their own at the local level, a problem that was “creeping slowly” for the state authorities but at the same time an existential problem for the farmers. This disparity in the conceiving the water problem in a national policy document shatters credibility and ability of policymakers. This

statement pays no attention to sustainability and environmental impact of ground water extraction at such a large scale. On the one hand, the document laments floods due to climate changes but on the other hand it celebrates the practices that consume fossil fuels and increase carbon emissions. This practice mocks at the most impressive and extensive irrigation network of canals in Pakistan. Groundwater abstraction declines water tables and causes environmental degradation thus it is unsustainable in the long run.

The document then reiterates rapid population growth, unregulated urbanization and climate change as three major factors responsible for water crisis. Water crisis is now framed as a “thunderbolt” (p. 3) instead of “creeping slowly”. This framing indicates a sudden and abrupt appearance of the problem but this suddenness is negated by the previous scenario presented in the document. All this framing shows that only “now” the matter has become urgent. The document itself admits at least that this water crisis is not unpredicted. Anyhow, the policy sets four conditions for the successful response to the water crisis: political support, national management, sustained commitment and institutional capacity. Irony is that that these four required conditions are already responsible for the water crisis and track record reflected in the policy shows that the picture is not bright in future. Political fluctuations, mismanagement, sustained negligence and depleting institutional capacities would likely remain constant national excuses in the policy discourse.

Second part of the Preamble of NWP outlines fifteen major concerns related to water crisis. First concern takes it for granted fact that fresh water is a “finite source” whose scarcity is progressing due to “its competing demands” (p. 3). It is true that fresh water is only a minor portion of earth water but only instrumental economic rationality assumes that this minimal proportion of fresh water is insufficient for human population. This logic entails that only scarcity needs management and conservation. The historical mismanagement and non-conservation record of state authorities and policymakers suggest that fresh water is never considered a “finite source” in Pakistan. Actual concern is not scarcity but fair allocation and distribution and thrifty usage of water.

Wastage of any resource can consume abundant quantities. Moreover, the concept of “competing demands” is quite ambiguous as it is not sure which demands are more urgent and why and how these demands have been created. In this way, the policy is following typical economic rationality of demand and supply, however, the laws of demand and supply are not natural. Second concern is about health, food and energy security. Logically, this concern arises only when the scarcity of water is presumed. Third concern is about climate change and vulnerability of Pakistan due to its geographic location. This concern is factually true but this facticity is not newly emerged. The same geography is now lamented that is otherwise celebrated strategically and politically. Same logic underlies in the concerns, objectives, principles and plans of the policy as the following glimpses from the policy text affirm.

Marketization of groundwater conservation

Water conservation is presented as the first strategic priority and principle in the policy. It states that along with lining of water courses “conservations measures can be adopted for ground water by regulating its extraction and use” (p. 8). This policy measure is typically grounded in neoliberal capitalist economic conceptions. In this conception, adopting conservation measures for groundwater by regulating its extraction and use is problematic for several reasons that the policy ignores. First risk is that of privatization of water resources and water management. Private entities control groundwater and prioritize profit over access. This can potentially exacerbate existing inequalities in which communities in desert areas specifically will suffer from restricted and expensive access to water sources. Second potential risk is market-based allocation of water which means higher pricing for water usage. Such a mechanism will adversely affect small farmers and poor households. Industries and rich people will be able to afford water rights but poor people will struggle for this fundamental need. Third risk is environmental harm. Extraction regulation may benefit conservation but economic gains will push back the concerns for sustainability in the long run. Finally, as is the convention in neoliberal practices, private corporations will exert influence leading to

regulatory capture thus can undermine the effectiveness of groundwater conservation goals. This neoliberal policy framework suggests that domestic extraction may be restricted or banned in the name of poor quality or other excuses. In other words, groundwater extraction such as hand-pumps in households will become virtually impossible and all citizens will be compelled to purchase water from corporations.

This neoliberal agenda is more clearly and loudly announced in next strategy as “adoption of new technologies” and as much possible encouragement of “investments aimed at start-up companies that promote remote sensing, demand side management and agricultural productivity” (p. 9). It appears a viable and rational solution at the first glance but instrumental rationality ignores long-term harms and risks. Remote sensing is possible only with routine data collection that will lead to privacy issues. Big-Tech and Big Data companies are already dominating in late neoliberal capitalism. Apart from this, introduction of new technologies can have unpredicted environmental impacts such as electronic waste and energy consumption. This possibility contradicts with the climate change concerns the policy has expressed regarding water issues. High-tech solutions will not only demand huge funds and investments from the state and corporations but they will also make it obligatory for the farmers and consumers to install appropriate technology to make the system functional. This will lead to concentration of resources leaving small farmers, companies and individuals outside the agriculture sector. The policy document resolves to appreciate “home-grown innovations” for technology leverage but in fact already established tech-giants will be served because “start-ups” are not always successful and runs the risks of failures and scaling up their innovations. Furthermore, the start-ups in emerging markets such as demand side management and remote sensing, are volatile as free market fluctuates unpredictably and regulatory regimes also change from time to time. Another potential problem is the adoption of innovation and new technology and delayed adoption can reduce returns on investments. After all, the end-user will pay all the costs and water usage will become extremely expensive for poor citizens.

Contradicting groundwater conservation and extraction

On the one hand, the policy announces regulation of extraction and use of groundwater for its conservation but conversely hopes the same extraction expansion will solve the power and water crisis. The policy document states “a large percentage of tube wells in Pakistan, can be converted to solar energy” (p. 9). This conversion to renewable energy source is viable strategy and have several benefits but it is idealistic in many ways. Investments for solar system installation may prove prohibitive for small farmers precisely who are needy due to lack of resources. Solar systems are not risk-proof. They require regular maintenance for their proper functioning. Tube wells are in rural and distant areas of Pakistan and these are the areas where technical expertise and services are limited, thus potential failures will add to costs for upkeep and repairs. Solar energy is considered a clean source of power but the production and disposal of solar panels have environmental impact. Panel manufacturing involves hazardous materials and disposal of expired panels involves electronic waste. Both of these factors contribute to environmental degradation and climate change, the problem for which these are thought as solutions. Again, the policy documents suggests “banning flood irrigation” (p. 16) because of water scarcity and alarming depths of groundwater tables but giving the solution of solar power it contradicts its own concerns. Solar powered tube wells will run continuously leading to depletion of already stressed aquifers because of over-extraction of groundwater. Regulation of water extraction through solar tube wells will create further problems for farmers.

Water policy document dominantly focusses on “efficient” or restricted use of water in agriculture; it is significant that no such emphasis is visible throughout the document for industry especially fashion, leather and sugar. Explaining the efficient use of water, apart from banning flood irrigation, the document proposes an Action Plan consisting of “extensive research and development for new varieties of crops with high yields, lower water consumption, reduced GHG emissions, resistant to heat stress, drought tolerant and less prone to insects and pests” (p. 16). The policymakers ignore the fact

that agricultural research and development requires huge investments resulting in higher costs of new varieties. Smallholders and poor farmers find difficult to buy new seeds every year. New seeds and varieties are developed often through private research thus typically patented. Companies with exclusive rights dominate agribusiness leading declining control of farmers over the seeds and its costs. As the history shows, every year new seeds and varieties of different crops are developed because every new variety has some problems. New varieties often have negative impact on biodiversity because adoption of few “efficient” crops reduces genetic pool and makes ecosystem vulnerable to pests and new diseases. The document makes lofty claim of developing new varieties through “extensive” research but neglects the fact that developing a variety with all the desired and stated traits simultaneously is scientifically complex and may not be feasible. Even if it is possible to get all the desired traits in certain crop varieties, it is not sure that such genetically modified crops will maintain nutritional contents, taste, texture and shelf-life as that of organic crops. While the policy encourages and envisions new crops developed through research and development, it becomes suddenly less modern and more conservative by encouraging “bio-fertilizers and bio-pesticides” (p. 17). The policy does not consider the introduction of bio-fertilizers/pesticides in current varieties and takes it for granted that new varieties will essentially be compatible with bio-fertilizers/pesticides.

Ambiguities in the status of water

National Water Policy document is quite ambiguous over the exact status of water. The policymakers are not sure whether water is a natural blessing included in commons or a commodity for profit earning. Document’s planning principle states that “access to affordable and safe drinking water is a fundamental human right of all citizens” (p. 10) whereas in irrigated agriculture it is declared as a “highly underpriced commodity” (p. 17). Human right status of water entails that clean and safe drinking water should be available to everyone irrespective of capacities to pay. It might be argued that there is a difference between drinking water and water for irrigation or industrial use but this argument is not

valid because drinking water may be used in irrigation/industries and irrigation water may be used for drinking purposes. Distinction between the two is that of uses not of nature of water and it is quite difficult to differentiate the two uses. Moreover, if water is a shared common then its commodification is ethically problematic. “Affordability” factor in case of drinking water also includes some economic touch of commodification as there is clear distinction between “free” and “affordable”. Affordable item is what can be bought repeated and regularly. It is not true that only irrigation water is priced but drinking water is also commodified as the document states “urban water tariffs must be revised” (p. 18) along with affordable pricing of rural water supply and sanitation (p. 18). It means that urban water will be priced according to “financial sustainability” irrespective of affordability of citizens. The policy completely forgets that drinking water is a fundamental right when it plans to reduce “non-revenue water allocation” (p. 18). It is unambiguous that citizens will have no bucket without bucks. Policymakers ignore even the element of affordability while suggesting to rationalize charges for irrigation water. Since the document is prepared in the background of emerging water crisis, water scarcity and high demand for it, it is quite implausible to discuss water tariffs because pricing of water cannot reduce natural demand, use and scarcity of water. Ironically, if irrigation water is fairly-priced then the thought of ban on flood irrigation contradicts consumer rights, free market principles and laws of demand and supply. A farmer purchasing water at fair price can use it in whatever way he likes. This commodification and pricing of drinking and irrigation water is clearly a neoliberal capitalist agenda that shatters all claims of citizen well-being and welfare propounded by the state. It appears that water policy is primarily framed for privatization, commodification and exploitation of water and water resources in the guise of emerging water crisis.

Neoliberal commodification of water

The neoliberal faith in privatization is more alarmingly pronounced in “leaving development of fresh groundwater entirely to the private sector” (p. 21). In addition, groundwater pumping will be

controlled or restricted “through enforcement of a strict regulatory framework” (p. 21). Here, policymakers are drowned in contradictions encouraging groundwater extraction through solar-powered tube wells, declaring drinking water as a fundamental human right, banning free drinking water to all citizens, planning to manage water resources through a national framework for the well-being of nation, handing over fresh groundwater to private companies and strictly regulating groundwater pumping. This neoliberal framework is imbued with capitalist exploitation and commodification but wrapped in national interest. What this emphasis on commodification of water suggests is that there is no real concern for increasing supply of water or managing existing water but the actual concern is to sell the available water under compulsory legal structures. Rationally, better pricing is only possible when a commodity is necessarily and intentionally kept scarce. Concealing true colors, the policy voices public participation for the easy enforcement of this capitalist water policy. Private capital investment and discipline is hoped to ensure cost savings, efficiency and competition in water management. This hope is based on Private Power Producers model. The policy labels it “fortunate” and “successful” investment model. Evidently, this fortune and success is only for the private capitalists who are greedy for profit and create cut-throat competition under monopolistic conditions. It is needless to say that Private Power Production has played havoc to the national economy of Pakistan and has made life of citizen difficult to the imagined limits. The price of electricity is progressively increasing on quarterly basis. Water policy is making this model an example and suggests to emulate this to counter so-called water crisis. If power policy is adopted in water policy then it can be safely projected that even drinking water will become unaffordable to majority of population of Pakistan. Under the spell of gender equality dominant in global policy discourses, the policymakers state that women participation “will be promoted in domestic water supply” and “water hygiene” (p. 23). There is complete silence for further details. It is unclear how women will participate in domestic water supply and hygiene or whether they are currently excluded from these practices.

CONCLUSION

National Water Policy of Pakistan is full of contradictions regarding fresh water, ground water and glacial melt. The policy consistently laments climate change and warns of glacial melt and flooding due to global warming on the one hand, but also celebrates the share of glacial melt in available river water. The document admits that glacial melt contributes 41% share to river flows (p. 32). It means glacial melt will increase river flow but it demands efficient management of this glacial water. In other words, the repeated claim of water scarcity and finitude (p. 3, 31, 36) is false as Pakistan is home to almost 7000 glaciers. It is quite sure that water sources are abundant and can effectively meet the demand of the population. Regarding groundwater, the policy admits that Pakistan has “already crossed the sustainable limit of safe yield” for groundwater extraction (p. 32). One wonders what the policy wants to convey and convince. If the sustainable limit of groundwater extraction is crossed then why increased extraction through solar tube wells is encouraged and why groundwater extraction is privatized for profit making and why simultaneously its pumping is to be strictly regulated. Moreover, if groundwater extraction limit is crossed and glacial fresh water is available due to climate change and heat wave then why glacial melt is feared. These contradictions remain unresolved in the water policy that appears to be devoid of deliberation and a fine example of copy-paste from different even conflicting sources. This policy is simply a plan for commodification of water, water taxation, privatization of water sources and simplistic promises for water crisis solution. On the basis of analysis it can said that this policy will create a worst kind of drinking water crisis in Pakistan making water a high-priced commodity controlled by capitalist market.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All the relevant data are included in the paper.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors declare no conflict.

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